

Implementation of ESD middleware at STFC and CMCC to support the demonstrator Milestone M9

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ESDM Prototype

Executive Summary

The ESDM middleware has been designed to allow interactions with different kinds of backend, by means of data storing and retrieval. Specifically, the ESDM middleware allows interactions with various backends, exploiting different specific plugins to enable connection and I/O operations on different storage types. These plugins are embedded into a pre-existing and generic core module able to support and expose all the interfaces needed to define I/O operations on the different backends; each specific plugin implements the interfaces to allow data management, storage, access and retrieval.

The design targets, but is not limited to, earth system data, addressing the challenges faced by domain scientist and data centre operators for usability and performance. The architecture builds on top of NetCDF and HDF5 but utilises scientific metadata to harness a data structure centric perspective while retaining well-established end-user interfaces. We demonstrate prototype capability by conducting a preliminary performance assessment of the middleware on different systems to illustrate the importance of adaptive data placement.

The milestone provides technical details of the deployments on the clusters at STFC, DKRZ, CMCC, and on a test system at Seagate, meeting the formal project requirement for deployment on these platforms. This deployment could be used to support future demonstrator applications, albeit not all features are completely implemented yet.

Deployment at STFC (JASMIN)

The ESDM was deployed in the JASMIN environment by compiling on a JASMIN science machine, with execution using the Lotus batch cluster and the Panasas POSIX parallel file system.

System description

JASMIN is a supercomputing environment targeted for data intensive analytics and long-term storage. The system includes a batch cluster, a community cloud, and a range of different storage partitions. The ESDM was compiled using a system deployed in the community cloud (a “JASMIN science machine”) utilising the RHEL6.1 O/S (kernel 2.6.32). The ESDM was deployed as test running on the LOTUS batch cluster using the Platform LSF scheduler. At the time of the test, LOTUS consisted of approximately 5000 cores of Intel Xeon utilising a range of different sockets (Lotus has been incrementally upgraded by adding new nodes over several years). JASMIN (and LOTUS) can exploit five different types of disk storage: PURE disk for the home file system, PANASAS parallel file storage (PFS), Quobyte file storage, Caringo Object storage, and cloud block storage. At the time of writing, only the PFS was configured for parallel write.

Deployment

Note: All scripts and configurations will be provided on a separate public GIT repository to allow reproduction of the results. We show relevant excerpts here.

JASMIN/Lotus

To support this cluster, a newer software stack of prerequisites is necessary. Firstly, OpenMPI 3.1 was build, then Spack to satisfy the dependencies for jansson, glib, cmake, and a C compiler supporting C11.

To compile ESDM with the preliminaries a typical setup was done loading dependencies:

```
$ export MODULEPATH=$MODULEPATH:/home/users/kunkel/install/modules
$ source /home/users/kunkel/spack/share/spack/setup-env.sh
$ module load kunkel/openmpi/3.1
$ spack load jansson glib gcc gettext cmake -r
```

and compiling ESDM:

```
$ ./configure --prefix=$HOME/esdm/install --with mpicc=$HOME/install/openmpi/3.1.0/bin/mpicc
```

We configured ESDM in its esdm.conf file to use the home and scratch file systems as follows:

```
{
  "esdm": {
    "backends": [
      {
        "type": "POSIX",
        "id": "scratch",
        "target": "/work/scratch/XX/_esdm",
        "performance-model": {
          "latency": 0.000001,
          "throughput": 500.0
        },
        "max-threads-per-node": 4,
        "max-fragment-size": 1048576000,
        "max-global-threads": 400,
        "accessibility": "global"
      }
    ],
    "metadata": {
      "type": "metadummy",
      "name": "md",
      "target": "/home/users/XX/_esdm",
      "accessibility": "global"
    }
  }
}
```

This configures ESDM to use only one backend under /work/scratch using a maximum of 4 threads per node to perform I/O. Data is partitioned into (max) 1 GB fragments.

Evaluation

We report here the baseline evaluation of the ESDM software infrastructure. It is carried out by running our own MPI benchmark that uses the ESDM interface. This benchmark partitions the rows of a quadratic 2D field across the different processes and writes a time series of these fields. Next, the time is measured while each process writes its complete data in one step, finally, the same process reads the data back. We store data on different storage backends (local vs. global) to assess the impact a decision component could have that selects the storage backends intelligently depending on data properties.

To verify that ESDM can be run at all, two runs were made with a 100k field (data size 763 GiB):

- a) 1 node with 4 processes. This resulted in a performance of 492 MiB/s and 290 MiB/s for read and write, respectively.
- b) 16 nodes and 4 processes per node yielding 4006 MiB/s and 1340 MiB/s for read and write, respectively.

Further testing needs to be made on this system to ensure correct behaviour.

Deployments at DKRZ (Mistral)

System Description

The German Climate Computing Center is a national service facility and a major partner for climate research. Its high performance computers, data storage and services form the central research infrastructure for simulation-based climate science in Germany.

The Mistral supercomputer features approx. 3.300 compute nodes bullx DLC 720 with a total of more than 100.000 cores resulting in a 3.6 Petaflop system.

The system was deployed in two phases. Phase 1 provides 1550 nodes with 2 Intel Xeon E5-2680v3 12C 2.5GHz ("Haswell") each, and Phase 2 added 1750 nodes with 2 Intel Xeon E5-2695V4 18C 2.1Ghz ("Broadwell") each.

DKRZ/Mistral

Support for this site requires to install a number of dependencies not available in the default software tree. This is the case for: jansson, glib.

```
$ module load openmpi cmake gcc
$ source /home/users/luettgau/spack/share/spack/setup-env.sh
$ spack load jansson glib
```

Configure ESDM using the following commands:

```
./configure --prefix=$HOME/esdm/install
```

If not configured otherwise, switch to out of tree build directory (default is: build) and use make to compile.

Configuration

The following configurations were used for the scenarios measured and plotted in the evaluation section.

local-only

```
{"esdm":
  {
    "backends": [
      {
        "type": "POSIX", "id": "tmp", "target": "/tmp/_esdm",
        "performance-model" : {"latency" : 0.000001, "throughput" : 500.0},
        "max-threads-per-node" : 4,
        "max-fragment-size" : 104857600,
        "max-global-threads" : 4000000,
        "accessibility" : "local"
      }
    ],
    "metadata": {
      "type": "metadummy",
      "name": "md",
      "target": "._metadummy",
      "accessibility" : "global"
    }
  }
}
```

lustre-both:

```
{"esdm":
  {
    "backends": [
```

```

        {"type": "POSIX", "id": "lustre01", "target": "/mnt/lustre01/work/ku0598/k202079/_esdm",
          "performance-model": {"latency": 0.000001, "throughput": 5000.0},
          "max-threads-per-node": 8,
          "max-fragment-size": 104857600,
          "max-global-threads": 400,
          "accessibility": "global"
        },
        {"type": "POSIX", "id": "lustre02", "target": "/mnt/lustre02/work/ku0598/k202079/_esdm",
          "performance-model": {"latency": 0.000001, "throughput": 5000.0},
          "max-threads-per-node": 8,
          "max-fragment-size": 104857600,
          "max-global-threads": 400,
          "accessibility": "global"
        }
      ],
      "metadata": {
        "type": "metadummy",
        "name": "md",
        "target": "./_metadummy",
        "accessibility": "global"
      }
    }
  }
}

```

lustre-both-large:

```

{"esdm":
  {
    "backends": [
      {"type": "POSIX", "id": "lustre01", "target": "/mnt/lustre01/work/ku0598/k202079/_esdm",
        "performance-model": {"latency": 0.000001, "throughput": 5000.0},
        "max-threads-per-node": 4,
        "max-fragment-size": 524288000,
        "max-global-threads": 400,
        "accessibility": "global"
      },
      {"type": "POSIX", "id": "lustre02", "target": "/mnt/lustre02/work/ku0598/k202079/_esdm",
        "performance-model": {"latency": 0.000001, "throughput": 5000.0},
        "max-threads-per-node": 4,
        "max-fragment-size": 524288000,
        "max-global-threads": 400,
        "accessibility": "global"
      }
    ],
    "metadata": {
      "type": "metadummy",
      "name": "md",
      "target": "./_metadummy",
      "accessibility": "global"
    }
  }
}

```

lustre02:

```

{"esdm":
  {
    "backends": [
      {"type": "POSIX", "id": "lustre02", "target": "/mnt/lustre02/work/ku0598/k202079/_esdm",
        "performance-model": {"latency": 0.000001, "throughput": 5000.0},
        "max-threads-per-node": 8,
        "max-fragment-size": 104857600,
        "max-global-threads": 400,
        "accessibility": "global"
      }
    ],
    "metadata": {

```

```

        "type": "metadummy",
        "name": "md",
        "target": "./_metadummy",
        "accessibility": "global"
    }
}

```

lustre02-large:

```

{"esdm":
  {
    "backends": [
      {"type": "POSIX", "id": "lustre02", "target": "/mnt/lustre02/work/ku0598/k202079/_esdm",
        "performance-model": {"latency": 0.000001, "throughput": 5000.0},
        "max-threads-per-node": 4,
        "max-fragment-size": 524288000,
        "max-global-threads": 400,
        "accessibility": "global"
      }
    ],
    "metadata": {
      "type": "metadummy",
      "name": "md",
      "target": "./_metadummy",
      "accessibility": "global"
    }
  }
}

```

tmpfs-only:

```

{"esdm":
  {"backends": [
    {"type": "POSIX", "id": "shm", "target": "/dev/shm/_esdm",
      "performance-model": {"latency": 0.000001, "throughput": 500.0},
      "max-threads-per-node": 0,
      "max-fragment-size": 104857600,
      "max-global-threads": 4000000,
      "accessibility": "local"
    }
  ],
  "metadata": {"type": "metadummy",
    "name": "md",
    "target": "./_metadummy",
    "accessibility": "global"
  }
}
}

```

Evaluation

We report results for different storage configurations on the Mistral supercomputer. The benchmark was run with 200k elements and 10 timesteps on 200 nodes at DKRZ for various numbers of processes per node (PPN); results are shown in Figure 1. It yields a performance of 200 GB/s (read) and 150 GB/s (write) on the Lustre02 file system. For comparison, performance has been measured with IOR and one file per process and using a similar data size and configuration.

IOR yielded similar results (175 GB/s read, 150 GB/s write with 8 PPN) but less performance with lower PPN since Lustre benefits from concurrent I/O on a node. ESDM uses multiple threads automatically and hence is able to improve performance for these cases.

Runs with less nodes yielded a higher throughput and efficiency per-node, but since we are interested in large scale, we omit them here.

Additional runs of the ESDM benchmark were conducted in a configuration where data was stored on both Lustre file systems concurrently. In that case, performance of the write path could be increased to 220 GiB/s, but the read performance was reduced. A reason is the prototypical implementation of the metadata handling right now. Additional tests were run to show the feasibility to utilize local (SSD and in-memory) storage as well, but they need further analysis of the unexpected node-local performance behaviour.

Figure 1: Read/write performance on DKRZ/Mistral

Deployment at CMCC

Two clusters have been considered: Athena and OphidiaLab.

Athena is the main HPC infrastructure of CMCC Super Computing Center (SCC) and used for data production. It is formed by 480 nodes equipped with a dual processor IBM iDataplex, thus providing a total of 7680 cores for the users. Each node has the following features:

- 2 Intel Sandy Bridge processors with 8 physical cores per socket
- Intel Xeon CPU E5-2670 0 @ 2.60 GHz
- 20 MB chipset cache

- 64 GB RAM
- 500 GB local disk
- Operating system: CentOS 6.2

Nodes are connected to each other by an Infiniband network 4xFDR providing a throughput up to 40 Gb/s. The file system adopted to share data among nodes is the General Parallel File System (GPFS, proprietary license of IBM).

OphidiaLab is a small cluster consisting of 5 nodes designed to provide a scientific data analytics environment based on Ophidia. Three nodes are equipped by the following CPUs:

- 2 Intel Ivy Bridge processors with 10 physical cores per socket
- Intel Xeon CPU E5-2660 v2 @ 2.20 GHz
- Support for hyper-threading: enabled (40 logical cores)

The CPUs of the other two nodes are:

- 2 Intel Broadwell processors with 10 physical cores per socket
- Intel Xeon CPU E5-2630 v4 @ 2.20 GHz
- Support for hyper-threading: enabled (40 logical cores)

All the nodes have:

- 256 GB RAM
- 930 GB local disk
- Operating system: CentOS 7.3

Nodes are connected to each other by a 10 Gigabit Ethernet switch. The file system adopted to share data among nodes is the Gluster File System (GFS, open-source).

In order to test and validate the WOS backend of ESD Middleware, a WOS storage cluster has been deployed at SCC. The cluster consists of 5 nodes (1 master and 4 slaves) deployed as virtual machines on top of a hypervisor having the following features:

- IBM System x3630
- 2 Intel Westmere processors with 6 physical cores per socket
- Intel Xeon CPU E5645 @ 2.40 GHz
- 24 GB RAM
- 6.35 TB disk

Each node of the cluster has the following features:

- 2 cores
- 4 GB RAM
- 65 GB local disk (50 GB available to store the objects)
- Operating system: CentOS 6.6

A virtual network (exploiting hypervisor emulation) has been configured and set up in order to connect the nodes of the cluster to each other. In addition, each node has a network interface configured to receive/send data directly from/to the real network interface of the hypervisor. This interface is physically connected to the Gigabit Ethernet switch used to connect compute nodes of OphidiaLab cluster described above.

Installation

For the installation phase of ESDM over Athena cluster the following configuration has been adopted.

```
module load INTEL/intel_xe_2015.3.187
module load CMAKE/cmake-3.3.0-rc1
module load GLIB/glib-2.46.2
module load LIBTOOL/libtool-2.4
module load IMPI/intel_mpi_5.0.3.048

export CC=mpiicc
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$LD_LIBRARY_PATH:/path/to/glib/glib-
2.46.2/lib:/path/to/dist/lib:/path/to/boost/lib:/path/to/jansson/lib
export PKG_CONFIG_PATH=$PKG_CONFIG_PATH:/path/to/glib/glib-2.46.2/lib/pkgconfig

./configure --with-hdf5=/path/to/esdm/install
```

Note that a specific version of MPI, suited for the Athena architecture, has been considered to enable parallel processing of ESDM test programs.

Regarding the installation of ESDM over OphidiaLab, first the file CMakeLists.txt of ESDM backend-data sources has been changed as follows in order to enable the WOS backend.

```
diff --git a/src/backends-data/CMakeLists.txt b/src/backends-data/CMakeLists.txt
index 0ea46ec..1ef36ee 100644
--- a/src/backends-data/CMakeLists.txt
+++ b/src/backends-data/CMakeLists.txt
@@ -21,7 +21,7 @@ if(BACKEND_CLOVIS)
     SUBDIRS(Clovis)
 endif()

-option(BACKEND_WOS "Compile backend for WOS support?" OFF)
+option(BACKEND_WOS "Compile backend for WOS support?" ON)
if(BACKEND_WOS)
    message(STATUS "WITH_BACKEND_WOS")
    add_definitions(-DESDM_HAS_WOS=1)
```

Then the following configuration command has been used in the installation phase (for each node of the OphidiaLab cluster).

```
./configure --enable-wos=/path/to/dist --with-boost=/path/to/boost
```

The libraries named “dist” and “boost” are required by the WOS backend to enable communications with the WOS cluster described above. They have also been installed over cluster nodes according to the WOS documentation.

Configuration

The tests related to backend POSIX have been performed using the following configuration. Maximum fragment size has been set to 32 GB.

```
{
  "esdm": {
    "backends": [
      {
        "type": "POSIX",
        "id": "p1",
        "target": "./_posix",
        "max-threads-per-node": 1,
        "max-fragment-size": 34359738369,
        "max-global-threads": 400,
        "accessibility": "global"
      }
    ],
    "metadata": {
      "type": "metadummy",
      "name": "md",
    }
  }
}
```

```

        "target": "._metadummy"
    }
}

```

For the tests related to WOS performance the following ESDM configuration has been adopted. Max fragment size has been set to 1 GB.

```

{
  "esdm": {
    "backends": [
      {
        "type": "WOS",
        "id": "w1",
        "target": "host=192.168.89.11;policy=test;",
        "max-threads-per-node": 1,
        "max-fragment-size": 1073741825,
        "max-global-threads": 1,
        "accessibility": "global"
      }
    ],
    "metadata": {
      "type": "metadummy",
      "name": "md",
      "target": "._metadummy"
    }
  }
}

```

The target line shows the IP address of WOS cluster frontend.

Evaluation

The evaluation of the ESDM middleware has been performed by means of two kinds of tests at CMCC premises. They evaluated the ESDM performance in read/write mode on the Athena HPC cluster over GPFS (ESDM POSIX mode) and over the aforementioned WOS cluster running ESDM on OphidiaLab (ESDM WOS mode).

Concerning the evaluation of ESDM on Athena, tests have been performed executing the IOR benchmark and ESDM exploiting the Posix plugin using the following configuration:

- Nodes: 5, 10, 20
- Processes per node: 1, 8, 16
- Data volume: 32 GB

Additional runs have also been performed with IOR on a single node.

Figure 2 shows the results obtained using the aforementioned configurations. Tests have been carried out in a production infrastructure in a shared file system environment.

Regarding the ESDM exploiting the deployed WOS cluster, tests have been carried out with ESDM (WOS mode) running on OphidiaLab compared to an ad-hoc developed application, which performs a simple transfer of data from the nodes memory to the WOS storage (write) and uses the RAM also to store data retrieved from the WOS (read).

To perform the tests, the following configuration has been used:

- Nodes: 5

- Processes per node: 1, 2, 4, 10, 20
- Data volume: 1 GB

A single serial run has also been performed. Figure 3 shows the results obtained in read and write mode using the WOS benchmark application and the ESDM middleware.

Figure 2: Read/write performance on Athena at CMCC

Figure 3: WOS Read/write performance on OphidiaLab at CMCC

Deployment at SEAGATE (Test system)

A prototype Clovis ESDM backend has been implemented. We have followed the following steps to configure and test this backend. Due to the nature of the test system, there was no performance investigation made.

Installing Mero

Please see: `“src/backends-data/Clovis/README.txt”`

You will need a CentOS 7.2 system to install Mero. Mero can run in both

cluster and singlenode modes. The singlenode mode can either use an available single drive for its data storage. It can also use multiple drives if they are available.

The instructions on this document are tested on a VirtualBox CentOS 7.2 VM. They are expected to work on real hardware and other virtualization software such as VMWare with similar configurations.

Update your installation to specific CentOS 7 kernel and related packages.
Boot into that kernel.

```
>> sudo yum install kernel-3.10.0-514.6.1.el7.x86_64
>> sudo yum install kernel-devel-3.10.0-514.6.1.el7.x86_64
>> sudo yum update --exclude=kernel*
>> reboot
```

Install epel-release and update packages if necessary.

```
>> sudo yum install epel-release -y
>> sudo yum update --exclude=kernel* -y
```

Mero requires lustre lnet for i/o communication. Set up yum repository for Intel Lustre 2.9 package.

```
>> cat /etc/yum.repos.d/lustre-intel.repo
[lustre-intel-2.9.0]
baseurl =
https://downloads.hpdd.intel.com/public/lustre/lustre-2.9.0/el7/client/
gpgcheck = 0
name = Intel - Lustre 2.9.0
```

Download Mero binary rpm packages.

```
>> ls Downloads/
mero-1.0.0-1_3.10.0_514.6.1.el7.x86_64.gitab0c26c.el7.centos.x86_64.rpm
mero-devel-1.0.0-1_3.10.0_514.6.1.el7.x86_64.gitab0c26c.el7.centos.x86_64.rpm
```

Make sure that kernel versions of your system matches that of the builds. Do not attempt to install Mero if they do not.

```
>> uname -r
3.10.0-514.6.1.el7.x86_64
```

Simply yum install Mero and Mero-devel rpm packages.

```
>> cd Downloads
>> sudo yum install mero-1*.rpm mero-devel-1*.rpm -y
```

Verify installation.

```
>> rpm -qa | grep mero-
mero-devel-1.0.0-1_3.10.0_514.6.1.el7.x86_64.gitab0c26c.el7.centos.x86_64
```

```
mero-1.0.0-1_3.10.0_514.6.1.el7.x86_64.gitab0c26c.el7.centos.x86_64
```

Or.

```
>> yum list installed mero*
```

```
Installed Packages
```

```
mero.x86_64 1.0.0-1_3.10.0_514.6.1.el7.x86_64.gitab0c26c.el7.centos installed
```

```
mero-devel.x86_64 1.0.0-1_3.10.0_514.6.1.el7.x86_64.gitab0c26c.el7.centos installed
```

Running Mero in single node configuration

```
>> sudo m0singlenode activate
```

```
---> Activating singlenode services
```

```
rm '/etc/systemd/system/mero-mkfs.service'
```

```
rm '/etc/systemd/system/mero.service'
```

```
rm '/etc/systemd/system/mero-client.service'
```

```
rm '/etc/systemd/system/mero-singlenode.service'
```

```
rm '/etc/systemd/system/mero-server-confd.service'
```

```
rm '/etc/systemd/system/mero-server-ha.service'
```

The successful execution of this command will enable all necessary single node services. This needs to be done only once after installing a fresh copy of Mero or upgrading an existing installation to a new version. See help for more details:

```
>> m0singlenode --help
```

Once you have successfully activated the single node Mero services you are now ready to configure storage for Mero. For VMs and hardware that do not have multiple disks Mero provide a single command that creates a number of image files as Mero's storage on their existing hard drive. This is achieved with the following command:

```
>> sudo m0setup -M
```

```
---> Requested configuration: [P=8 N=2 K=1] with 1 ioservice(s), 64GiB disks in '/var/mero'
```

```
---> Removing loop devices
```

```
---> Removing file images
```

```
---> Creating 8 file images, 64GiB each, in '/var/mero'
```

```
---> Setting up loop devices
```

```
---> Generating genders file '/etc/mero/genders'
```

```
---> Generating disks-*.conf files
```

```
---> Starting mero-mkfs, this may take a while...
```

Notice that the image files are created in the /var/mero directory.

The above setup needs to be performed only once. It erases all data and format the storage devices for Mero.

Mero runs just like any other Linux daemons. Use the following commands to start, stop, restart and check the status of Mero. See commands and example outputs below.

Start:

```
>> sudo m0singlenode start
```

```
---> Starting mero-singlenode services
```

```
---> waiting for lnet [ OK ]
```

```
---> waiting for mero-kernel [ OK ]
```

```
---> waiting for mero-server-ha [ OK ]
```

```
---> waiting for mero-server-confd      [ OK ]
---> waiting for mero-server@mds .      [ OK ]
---> waiting for mero-server@ios1      [ OK ]
---> waiting for mero                    [ OK ]
---> waiting for mero-client            [ OK ]
---> waiting for mero-singlenode        [ OK ]
```

Stop:

```
>> sudo m0singlenode stop
```

Please ignore the HA service failed error messages when stopping Mero. This is a known issue in Singlenode Mero. HA service stops properly on cluster mode.

Restart:

```
>> sudo m0singlenode restart
```

Status:

```
>> sudo m0singlenode status
```

```
### Global state -----
```

```
State:          loaded
Autostart:       disabled
LNet:           active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:08:26 GMT
LNet Network ID: 10.0.2.15@tcp
```

```
### Kernel -----
```

```
mero-kernel     active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:02 GMT
m0ctl           44181  1
m0mero          4238578 6 m0ctl
m0gf            121518 1 m0mero
lnet            351271 3 m0mero,ksocklnd
libcfs          521557 3 lnet,m0mero,ksocklnd
```

```
### Servers -----
```

```
mero-server-ha  active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:02 GMT  PID:7786
mero-server-confd active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:02 GMT  PID:7960
mero-server@mds active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:03 GMT  PID:8145
mero-server@ios1 active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:04 GMT  PID:8371
```

```
### Trace -----
```

```
mero-trace@kernel active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:02 GMT
mero-trace@ha   active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:02 GMT
mero-trace@confd active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:02 GMT
mero-trace@mds  active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:03 GMT
mero-trace@ios1 active  Fri 2016-11-18 11:11:04 GMT
```

The above commands can be executed as often as you like to start, stop, restart and check the status of Mero service on the system.

Building ESDM Clovis backend

Turning on the “BACKEND_CLOVIS” option in “src/backends-data/CMakeLists.txt”:

```
option(BACKEND_CLOVIS "Compile backend for Clovis support?" ON)
if(BACKEND_CLOVIS)
    message(STATUS "WITH_BACKEND_CLOVIS")
    add_definitions(-DESDM_HAS_CLOVIS=1)
    SUBDIRS(Clovis)
endif()
```

Configuring the MERO header file and lib file directory

In file “src/backends-data/Clovis/CMakeLists.txt”:
set(MERO_DIR "/some/path/to/mero_include_and_lib")

You need to modify this to the actual path. If you have installed mero-devel with default configuration, this path would be: “/usr”. If you have installed mero-devel in some other directory, please modify this setting to the actual directory.

Building ESDM with Clovis

Please follow the regular ESDM building process. No special requirements here.

Preparing ESDM Clovis conf

First, please identify the IP address of the node, on which the Mero is running. Here, we run Mero in single-node mode. So, the IP address is the local IP address.

This can be queried with:

```
[root@centos7-devvm ~]# lctl list_nids
192.168.168.146@tcp
[root@centos7-devvm ~]#
```

Now, please prepare a conf file like this:

```
$ cat src/test/_esdm.conf
{"esdm":
  {"backends": [
    {"type": "CLOVIS", "id": "c1", "target": ":12345:33:103 192.168.168.146@tcp:12345:34:1
<0x7000000000000001:0> <0x7200000000000001:64>"}
  ],
  "metadata": {"type": "metadummy", "id": "md", "target": "._metadummy"}
}
```

Please note that, the above IP address from `lctl list_nids` is the same as that in the configuration file.

Running ESDM with Clovis backend

If you have installed mero-devel in some other directory than the default “/usr” directory, you have to preload the lib. So, please run the test like this:

```
[root@centos7-devvm test]# LD_PRELOAD=/some/path/to/mero_include_and_lib/lib/libmero.so ./readwrite
```

or

```
[root@centos7-devvm test]# LD_PRELOAD=/mero.bin/lib/libmero.so ./readwrite-benchmark
```

If the mero lib has been installed to default “/usr” dir, you can omit the LD_PRELOAD.